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Microbial Quality of Water Stored in Storage Tanks at Female Hostels C And D Of The Federal Polytechnic Nekede Owerri

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ABSTRACT

The microbial quality of water stored in storage tanks at female hostels C and D of the Federal Polytechnic Nekede Owerri was carried out in this study using standard microbiological techniques. The results of the microbial load of the water samples from water storage tanks at Hostels C and D of Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri revealed that the Total viable count of the water samples ranged from 3.0×10^2 cfu/ml to 2.3×10^3 . The Hostel C had higher viable bacterial counts when compared with the Hostel D water samples. Water tanks from Hostel C only showed coliform count and *Escherichia coli* counts of 3.0×10^1 cfu/ml each. Also water tanks from hostel C only showed fungal counts of 3.0×10^1 cfu/ml and 7.0×10^1 cfu/ml respectively. The bacterial isolates obtained in this study were *Bacillus* species, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella* species, *Micrococcus* species, *Escherichia coli* and *Chromobacterium* species. The only fungal isolate obtained was *Candida* species. This suggests that microbial contamination of water is majorly bacteriological than fungal. The presence of these microorganisms is of public health concern since they have been implicated in causing water-borne diseases. There is therefore need for the authorities in the higher institutions to have a regular check on the cleanliness of the water tanks to ensure that the water provided in higher institutions is potable.

Keywords: Viable, isolates, bacterial, portable, diseases.

INTRODUCTION

Unsafe water poses a global public health threat, particularly affecting young children in developing countries. Each year, over 2 million people, mainly children under five, die from diarrheal disease, accounting for 17% of all deaths from 2000 to 2003. Nearly 90% of diarrheal-related deaths are attributed to unsafe water supplies and sanitation conditions. In Nigeria, 90 million people lack access to safe drinking water, and 130,000 under five children die annually from preventable waterborne diseases. Access to clean water is crucial for sustainable development, health, food production, and poverty reduction. Diarrhea remains the second leading cause of death among children under five globally, with 1.5 million deaths each year due to diarrhea. In Nigeria, drinking water is commercially available in

sachet water. Meeting microbiological standards is essential to reduce the spread of water-borne diseases and ensure wholesome and palatable water. Improper storage conditions in water storage tanks in student hostels can lead to waterborne diseases, necessitating the assessment of microbiological quality. Determining the bacterial load of water available to students in their hostels is important in assessing the microbial contamination of the water samples as well as the sources of contamination and possible disease occurrence associated with the water samples.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Samples

Different water samples available to campus hostels C and D of Fedponek were collected with sterile containers and transported to the laboratory for microbiological analysis.

Microbiological analysis of the Samples

The method described by Akani *et al.* (2021) was adopted in the study. One millilitre (1ml) of the samples were measured and placed in nine millilitre (9ml) of sterile water contained in a test tube and allowed to stand for about ten minutes to obtain a solution of the water samples ; thereafter one millilitre (1ml) of the solution were serially diluted using ten-fold serial dilution.

After the serial dilution, 0.1ml of the 10⁻¹ dilution was aseptically inoculated onto sterile plates of nutrient agar, MacConkey agar standard culture media for enumeration of microorganisms. After inoculating the sterile media, they were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours for the bacteriological media. After the incubation periods, the microorganisms enumerated on the culture plates were counted using the colony counter.

Identification of bacterial isolates

Gram Staining Techniques

A smear of each of the bacterial isolates were made and fixed by air drying. The smears were then be covered with crystal violet stain for 60 seconds and rapidly washed off with water thereafter. The smears were then be covered with Lugol's iodine for 60 seconds and washed off with water. Thereafter, the smears were decolorized with acetone alcohol and washed off after 10 seconds. Finally, the smears was flooded with safranin for 2minutes and washed off with clean water. The back of the slides wiped and placed in a draining rack for the smear to dry before they were viewed with x 100 oil immersion objective lens (Cheesbrough, 2005). Gram positive bacteria will give purple coloration while gram negative bacteria were given pinkish coloration.

Spore Staining

A smear of each of the bacterial isolates was made on clean grease – free slide and fixed by air drying. The smears were then covered with malachite green and placed over steam for 5 minutes while topping the slides with more malachite green when they are dried out. At the end of 5 minutes, the smears was washed off with clean water and counter stained with safranin for 2 minutes and washed off again with water. The smears were then allowed to dry before they were viewed with x 40 oil immersion objective lens. Spore positive slides will give a co-appearance of pink and green colour while negative slides were given only pinkish colouration (Cappuccino *et al.*, 2020).

Motility Test

Half strength nutrient agar was prepared, 14 grams per liter. 10mls of the prepared half strength agar were added in tubes and allowed to solidify. A sterile wire loop was used to pick the test organism and stab inoculates the tube in an upright position and then incubated for 18 hours. Motile organisms grew away from the line of stab while non-motile organisms grew along the line of stab (Mmuoegbulam, *et al* 2017).

Catalase Test

This test is used to differentiate those bacteria that produce the enzyme catalase such as *staphylococci* from non-catalase producing bacteria such as *Streptococci*.

About 2ml of hydrogen peroxide solution was poured into several test tubes for each of the bacterial isolates. Using a sterile wooden stick, each colony of the bacterial isolates was immersed in each of the hydrogen peroxide solution. Active bubbling within 10 seconds is an indication of a positive test while none is an indication of a negative test (Otorokpa, 2019).

Citrate Utilization Test

This test helps in the identification of enterobacteriaceae. Each of the test organisms was inoculated into sterile agar slopes of simmon citrate agar in each case using stab inoculation technique. The inoculated agar slopes were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. A bright blue coloration is an indication of a positive test while none is an indication of a negative test (Otokpa, 2019).

Indole Test

Some microorganisms are capable of hydrolyzing the amino acid Tryptophan and one of the end products is indole. The ability of a microbe to carry out this reaction can be used for biochemical characterization in the indole test.

The test organisms were suspended in sterile peptone (about 3ml) preparation in sterile test tubes and incubated at 37°C for 48 hours after which 0.5ml of kovac's reagent was added and shaken gently. A red coloration in the surface layer within 10 minutes is an indication of a positive test while none is an indication of a negative test (Otokpa, 2019).

Oxidase Test

The method of Sampson *et al.*, (2019) was adopted for this test. A piece of filter paper was placed in a clean Petri-dish and three drops of freshly prepared oxidase reagent was added in each case of the test organism. With a sterile piece of stick, each colony of the test organism was removed and smeared on each oxidase reagent drop on the filter paper. The development of a blue-purple coloration is an indication of a positive test while none is an indication of a negative test.

Sugar Fermentation Test

Each colony of the different test organisms was inoculated onto sterile agar slopes of triple sugar iron agar using stab inoculation. After this, the inoculated, agar slopes were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The different colours of the slopes and butts in addition to the presence of gas production and hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) blackening is indicative of the type of bacteria present (Sampson *et al.*, 2019)).

Coagulase Test

A drop of distilled water was placed on each of the test organisms. Thereafter a colony of each of the test organisms was emulsified in each of the drops to make a thick suspension. A loopful of plasma were then added to one of the suspension and mixed gently for each of the test organisms. Clumping of the organism within 10 seconds is an indication of a positive test while none is an indication of a negative test (Sampson *et al.*, 2019)

Lactophenol Cotton Blue Staining Technique

The fungal isolates were identified by morphological characteristics on Saboraund Dextrose Agar (SDA) and microscope examination after lactophonol cotton blue staining technique.

Each of the fungal isolates was separately collected with a sterile wooden stick and teased out on a drop of lactophenol cotton blue stain on a clean glass slide. The wet mount preparation was then viewed under the microscope for branched and unbranched hypahe (Henriot *et al.*, 2019).

RESULTS

The results of the microbial load of the water stored in storage tanks at Hostels C and D of Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri is presented in Table 4.1., Table 4.2 is the result of the identification of the bacterial isolates. The results of the identification of the fungal isolates is presented in Table 4.3 while Table 4.4 is the result of the percentage occurrences of the bacterial isolates.

Table 1: Microbial load of the water stored in storage tanks at Hostels C and D of Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri

Sample	Total viable count (cfu/ml)	Total coliform count (cfu/ml)	Total <i>E. coli</i> count (cfu/ml)	Total Fungal count (cfu/ml)
C1	2.1 x 10 ³	2.0 x 10 ³	3.0 x 10 ¹	3.0 x 10 ¹
C2	2.3 x 10 ³	-	-	7.0 x 10 ¹
D1	1.3 x 10 ³	-	-	-
D2	3.0 x 10 ²	-	-	-

Key: C1 and C2 are water samples from Hostel C
 D1 and D2 are water samples from Hostel D
 cfu/ml= colony forming units per millilitre

Table 2: Identification of the Fungal Isolates

Sample	Macroscopic Characteristics	Microscopic Characteristics	Possible Fungi
C1	Creamy raised non mucoid colonies	Budded yeast cells	<i>Candida</i> species

Table 3: Percentage Occurrence of the Bacterial Isolates from the Water Samples.

Isolate	Number of samples present	Number of samples where occurrence	Percentage occurrence (%)
<i>Bacillus</i> species	4	4	21.05
<i>Pseudomonas</i> species	4	4	21.05
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	4	4	21.05
<i>Salmonella</i> species	4	4	21.05
<i>Micrococcus</i> species	4	1	5.26
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	4	1	5.26
<i>Chromobacterium</i> spp	4	1	5.26
Total		19	100

DISCUSSION

The results of the microbial load of the water samples from water storage tanks at Hostels C and D of Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri as presented in Table 1 revealed that the Total viable count of the water samples ranged from 3.0 x 10² cfu/ml to 2.3 x 10³. The Hostel C had higher viable bacterial counts when compared with the Hostel D water samples. Water tanks from Hostel C only showed coliform count and *Escherichia coli* counts of 3.0 x 10¹ cfu/ml each. Also water tanks from hostel C only showed fungal counts of 3.0 x 10¹ cfu/ml and 7.0 x 10¹ cfu/ml respectively. Odigie *et al.*, (2021) reported microbial load of stored ground water utilized by undergraduates in Edo state. In their study, the total viable count ranged from 1.1 x 10² cfu/ml to 3.2 x 10² cfu/ml. This is considerably lower than the microbial load of the tanks assessed in this study. The reason for the discrepancy can be attributed to the level of disinfection of the water and cleaning of the storage tanks in the two different institutions. The level of hygiene in disinfection of the water and cleaning of the storage tanks may also explain the high bacterial load reported by Akinkugbe and Adedeji (2023) who reported bacterial load as high as 3.81 x 10⁶ cfu/ml in water tanks in Halls of residence at Achievers University Owo, Ondo state.

Ground water forms the ultimate source of boreholes. In the local population of Nigeria, borehole water serves as the major source of drinking water (Akpoveta *et al.*, 2011). Unfortunately, borehole water is not entirely pure and its purity depends on the geographical conditions of the soil. Contamination of water sources arise from human activities, such as disposal or dissemination of chemicals and microbial matter on the land surface and into soils, or through injection of wastes directly into groundwater.

The bacterial isolates obtained in this study were *Bacillus* species, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella* species, *Micrococcus* species, *Escherichia coli* and *Chromobacterium* species (Table 2)

Adeyemi *et al.*, (2020) also reported the presence of *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella* species, *Micrococcus* species and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. This is in line with the outcome of this work. *Escherichia coli* is a coliform which are important markers for bacteriological water quality as they are established causes for human gastro-enteritis and their presence in potable water makes it unfit for consumption. *E. coli* is the most implicated coliform.

The incidence of high numbers of *Pseudomonas* in potable water often elicits foul odour, taste, and high turbidity levels. *Salmonella* also isolated in this study clinically manifests in gastroenteritis in humans and one of its serotype-*typhi* causes typhoid fever with devastating public health implications (WHO 2017).

Sule *et al.*, (2011) also isolated *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, from stored drinking water in Illorin. This is also in agreement with the outcome of this study.

Bacillus species, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella* species had the highest percentage occurrence of 21.05% each while *Micrococcus* species, *E. coli* and *Chromobacterium* species had percentage occurrence of 5.26% each. The only fungal isolate obtained was *Candida* species. This suggests that microbial contamination of water is majorly bacteriological than fungal.

CONCLUSION

The outcome of this work has showed that the storage tanks at Hostels C and D of the Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri are contaminated with microorganisms of public health concern. More bacterial contaminants were recorded than fungal contaminants. These microorganisms included *Bacillus* species, *Pseudomonas* species, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella* species, *Micrococcus* species, *Escherichia coli*, *Chromobacterium* species and *Candida* species. The presence of these microorganisms is a cause for public health concern since they have been implicated in causing diseases especially in immunocompromised persons.

The results gotten in this study has necessitated the following recommendations:

1. Waste disposal systems in the hostels should be assessed periodically to ensure that waste dumps are not located close to boreholes where sewages may have interaction with the underground water sources causing contamination.
2. Students in the hostels should ensure that they do boil their water before consumption to eliminate pathogenic microorganisms.
3. The water storage tanks in public school hostels should be properly washed and regularly cleaned regularly by the responsible authorities to improve student's health and reduce cases of water borne diseases.

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